
Biomedical Applications of Electromagnetic Energy Workshop

July 17, 2019

The Bath Royal Literary and Scientific Institution,
BRLSI

United Kingdom

www.sumcastec.eu

www.creomedical.com

About SUMCASTEC

Semiconductor-based Ultrawideband Micromanipulation of CAncer STEM Cells (SUMCASTEC) explores radically new approach for cancer stem cells (CSCs) real time isolation (i.e. within minutes vs current 40 days) and neutralization. A novel micro-optofluidic lab-on-chip (LOC) platform will be developed through a joint and iterative efforts by biologists, clinicians and engineers. For the first time, a single LOC will be able to deliver ultra-wide broadband radiation to compare cell spectral signatures, image subcellular features, and hence modulate CSCs microenvironment conditions with unprecedented space and time resolution. It will be driven to isolate CSCs from heterogeneous differentiated and stem cell populations, and force CSCs differentiation, ultimately inducing sensitivity to anticancer treatments. In vitro and in vivo testing along with biophysical modelling will validate the approach and establish the proof-of-principle within the project lifetime, while laying the groundwork for further development of future electrosurgical tools that will be capable CSCs neutralization in tissue. This will not only establish a new line of treatment for brain cancers such as Glioblastoma Multiforme and Medulloblastoma, whose initiation and recurrence were linked to CSCs, and that claim tremendous human and economic tolls, worldwide. It will also push the current boundaries of microbiological analysis by enabling microenvironment characterization/manipulation and real-time ionic channels monitoring without cytotoxic patch-clamping or electron microscopy.

For more information please visit the website: www.sumcastec.eu

About Creo Medical

At Creo Medical we are dedicated to improving patient outcomes by bringing advanced energy to therapeutic endoscopy.

Our integrated electrosurgery unit delivers Bipolar Radiofrequency for precise dissection and resection and Microwave energy for controlled ablation and coagulation. This technology sets a new standard for Endoscopic Submucosal Dissection with our new Speedboat RS2 instrument: the Bipolar Radiofrequency cut allows precise dissection and the microwave coagulation provides controlled haemostasis while the protective hull reduces the risk of muscle damage and the integrated injection needle helps to maintain submucosal lift without instrument changes.

For more information please visit the website: <http://creomedical.com>

Acknowledgments

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Biomedical Application of Electromagnetic Energy Workshop Programme Proceedings

Technical Presentation Talks

Structure: 20 minutes talk, 5 minutes for Questions

Presenters are highlighted in the list of authors (**bold** and underlined).

All talks will be held in Elwin.

Time	Presentations	Room
09.00 – 09.15	Registration, Tea / Coffee.	Duncan
09.15 – 09.30	Welcome.	Elwin
09.30 – 10.00	Ultrashort Electric Pulses: a Way to Sensitize Cancer Stem Cells. <u>M. Tanori</u> , <i>ENEA, Italy</i> .	Elwin
10.00 – 10.30	Modulation of Intracellular Calcium Levels, in Glioblastoma Cells, Using Nanosecond Pulsed Electric Fields. <u>L. Carr</u> , <i>Univ. Limoges, France and Bangor University, UK</i> .	Elwin
10.30 – 11.00	From Eureka to Clinical Trials. <u>S. Chaudhry</u> , <i>Afon Technology Ltd, UK</i> .	Elwin
11.00 – 11.20	Tea / Coffee and Poster Presentation.	Duncan
11.20 – 11.50	The Antimicrobial Efficacy of a Combined RF and Microwave Energy Based Non-Thermal Plasma Generation System; Applications in the Medical Sector. <u>R. MS. Thorn</u> , <i>University of the West of England, UK</i> .	Elwin
11.50 – 12.20	A Pre-clinical Assessment of a Medical Microwave Ablation Device in the Treatment of Hepatic Cancer. <u>P. Sibbons</u> , <i>Creo Medical, UK</i> .	Elwin
12.20 – 12.50	High Voltage Controllable RF Source and Applicator for Electrosurgical Applications. <u>E. Waller</u> , <i>Bangor University, UK</i> .	Elwin
12.50 – 13.40	Lunch and Poster Presentation.	Duncan
13.40 – 14.10	Miniature Flexible Microwave Applicator for the Ablation of Pancreatic Tumours at 5.8GHz. <u>W. Tapplin</u> , <i>Bangor University, UK and Creo Medical, UK</i> .	Elwin
14.10 – 14.40	An Advanced System for the Visualisation and Treatment of Cancerous Nodules. <u>A. Jones</u> , <i>Bangor University, UK and Creo Medical, UK</i> .	Elwin
14.40 – 15.10	Nano-Imaging of Biological Cells Using High Refractive Index Barium Titanate Glass (BTG) Microspheres on Lab on Chip Platform. <u>R. Dhama</u> , <i>Bangor University, UK</i> .	Elwin
15.10 – 15.30	Tea / Coffee and Poster Presentation.	Duncan

15.30 – 16.00	UHF-Dielectrophoresis Crossover Frequency Measurements do Allow Discriminating Cancerous Stem Cells From Differentiated Cells. <u>A. Pothier</u> , <i>Univ. Limoges, France.</i>	Elwin
16.00 – 16.30	Creating Biological Scaffolds and Matrices for Clinical Application. <u>T. Ansari</u> , <i>Creo Medical, UK.</i>	Elwin
16.30 – 17.00	Potential Use of Porcine Gastro-Intestinal Organoids for Pharmacological Applications. <u>A. Olayanju</u> , <i>Northwick Park Institute for Medical Research, UK.</i>	Elwin
17.00 – 17.30	Closing and Networking.	Duncan

Posters Presentation

An interactive poster session will be presented during the Tea / Coffee and the Lunch. The presentation will be in front of your poster.

Presenters are highlighted in the list of authors (**bold** and underlined)

All Posters will be presented in Duncan

Poster #1	The Biological Effects of Microwave Electric Fields on Bacterial and Yeast Cells and Applications in Pathogen Detection. <u>E. K. Ahortor</u> , <i>Cardiff University, UK.</i>
Poster #2	A Novel Miniature Tissue Resection Device with Moveable Jaws that Combines 400 KHz and 5.8G Hz Energy for Cutting and Coagulation. <u>L. Turner</u> , <i>Bangor University, UK and Creo Medical, UK.</i>
Poster #3	An Example of a Medical Microwave System Developed by Members of The Group for the Treatment and Measurement of Breast Tumours. <u>C. Hancock</u> , <i>Bangor University, UK and Creo Medical, UK.</i>
Poster #4	Electrosurgical Applicator Radio Frequency; 100kHz 400V pk– pk Generator. <u>E. Waller</u> , <i>Bangor University, UK.</i>
Poster #5	Ultrashort Electric Field Pulse Generator using Avalanche Breakdown Transistors and the Open Circuit Transmission Line Technique. <u>I. W. Davies</u> , <i>Bangor University, UK and Creo Medical, UK.</i>
Poster #6	Push-Pull Configuration of High Power MOSFETs for Generation of Nanosecond Pulses for Electroporation of Medulloblastoma Cells. <u>I. W. Davies</u> , <i>Bangor University, UK and Creo Medical, UK.</i>
Poster #7	μ Pulse Electric Fields Exposure Targeting Medulloblastoma Cancer Stem Cells. <u>M. Tanori</u> , <i>ENEA, Italy.</i>
Poster #8	Human Medulloblastoma Cell Lines: Investigating on Cancer Stem Cell-Like Phenotype. <u>A. Casciati</u> , <i>ENEA, Italy.</i>

- Poster #9 **Microsystem and Lab-On-Chip Technologies Might Promote Future Generation of New Tools for Biological Analysis: Example of New Type of Cell Sorting Microsystem Taking Advantage of High Frequency Dielectrophoresis Specificities of Cancerous Cells.**
T. Provent, *Univ. Limoges, France.*
- Poster #10 **Glioblastoma Cancer Stem-like Cells Discrimination by UHF-Dielectrophoresis Crossover Frequency.**
S. Saada, *Univ. Limoges, France.*
- Poster #11 **Potential Use of Porcine Gastro-Intestinal Organoids for Safety Assessment of Current and Novel Chemical Entities.**
A. Olayanju, *Northwick Park Institute for Medical Research, UK.*
- Poster #12 **A Prototype System for Visualising and Treating Early Stage Cancerous Nodules within the Lungs.**
A. Jones, *Bangor University, UK and Creo Medical, UK.*

Technical Presentation Talks

Title

Ultrashort Electric Pulses: a Way to Sensitize Cancer Stem Cells.

Authors

M. Tanori¹, A. Casciati¹, P. Giardullo¹, B. Benassi¹, B. Tanno¹, A. Zambotti¹, R. Pinto¹, I. W. Davies^{3, 4}, C. Palego⁴, C. Hancock³, C. Marino¹, M. Mancuso¹ and C. Merla¹.

Affiliations

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2. *Department of Radiation Physics, Guglielmo Marconi University, Rome, Italy.*
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4. *School of Computer Science and Electronic Engineering, Bangor University, Bangor, UK.*

Abstract

Medulloblastoma (MB) is the most common pediatric malignant brain tumor, its conventional therapy consists of surgical resection followed by chemotherapy and radiotherapy that often involve severe neurocognitive deficiencies. Cancer stem cells (CSCs) seem to be candidates in the onset of the disease and constitute an endless reserve for the maintenance and progression of the tumor. These cells could be the reason of conventional therapy failure, maintaining a quiescence state that is the survival strategy responsible for later recurrence and relapse of the disease. Therefore, new therapeutic strategies are necessary to specifically target CSCs that escape from conventional treatments [1]. The aim of this study is to attempt to selectively target quiescent CSCs using suitable pulse electric fields (PEFs). Recently, pulsed electric fields in the microsecond and nanosecond time scale have been delivered to different cell types reporting different and interesting effects without thermal heating [2-4]. Our hypothesis is that the electric treatment would make CSCs more sensitive to radiotherapy by inducing stress effects, and or differentiation.

Therefore, as first step, different MB cell lines (D283, D341 and DAOY) were characterized in terms of their CSCs content. The D283 cells resulted a perfect model of MB SCs. They showed almost 100% of CD133 positive cells defining their high oncogenic potential, a major capacity to form neurospheres and to engraft in nude mice with respect to the other characterized cell lines.

Cell exposure was performed in standard electroporation cuvette using a suitable pulsing buffer [5, 6]. Different sets of delivered pulses were taken into account: microsecond pulses last 40 μ s with an amplitude of 0.35 MV/m, while nanosecond pulses last 300 ns with an amplitude of 1.1 MV/m. A variable number of pulses were also taken into account.

We analyzed different biological end points at different times after the exposure as: i) cell viability, ii) cell permeabilization, iii) cell cycle, iv) reactive oxygen species formation, as well as a panel of different genes involved in cell cycle, apoptosis and differentiation.

However, a crucial point for the effectiveness of this novel treatment strategy involves the selective neutralization of CSCs. To this aim normal human astrocyte (NHA), as a model of non-transformed cells, were exposed to similar electric stimulations. NHA presented

different responses with respect to D283 in term of cell membrane permeabilization, cell viability and cell cycle perturbation.

The evidenced selectivity of the electric treatment is very interesting for its potentiality in real therapeutic applications. Indeed, a combined treatment PEFs-ionizing radiation could represent an innovative strategy to improve clinical outcomes of MB in a near future.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 737164 Sumcastec

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- [3] M. Breton, L. M. Mir, Microsecond and nanosecond electric pulses in cancer treatments. *Bioelectromagnetics*, 33 106-123, 2012.
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- [5] I. Davis et al., Push-Pull Configuration of High Power MOSFETs for generation of nanosecond pulses for electropermeabilization of Cells *Int. J. of Microwave and Wireless Technologies*, accepted 2019.
- [6] Kenaan et al., Characterization of a 50- Ω exposure setup for high-voltage nanosecond pulsed electric field bioexperiments, *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, 58(1) 207-214, 2011.

Title

Modulation of Intracellular Calcium Levels, in Glioblastoma Cells, using Nanosecond Pulsed Electric Fields.

Authors

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Affiliations

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2. School of Computer Science and Electronic Engineering, Bangor University, Bangor, UK.

Abstract

Calcium ions (Ca^{2+}) play a key role in a wide range of cellular processes, with elevation of intracellular Ca^{2+} levels being seen by cells as a signalling event. Ca^{2+} is involved in gene transcription, metabolism, muscle contraction as well as cell development, differentiation, proliferation and death [1,2]. The ability to influence such a wide range of processes is due to tight control of calcium by many different molecular contributors that control its spatio-temporal patterning [3]. Calcium signals within the cell originate from either an influx of extracellular calcium or from the release of calcium from intracellular stores, predominately the endoplasmic and sarcoplasmic reticulums (ER and SR).

Nanosecond pulsed electric fields (nsPEF) are ultrashort pulses (generally 1-300 ns duration) with high electric field intensity (> 10 kV/cm) [4] and are considered as non-thermal. When applied to cells in vitro they have been shown to induce cell death that is believed to follow an apoptotic pathway. Research in the field focuses largely on the application of nsPEF as a treatment for cancer. Work in both animal models and humans has shown that nsPEF can reduce the size of tumours [5–7], whilst also stimulating an immune response against the cancer cells [8]. In vitro studies have shown numerous effects of nsPEF on cells including permeabilisation of both the plasma membrane and organelle membranes [9][10][5] and changes in intracellular calcium levels [11][12][13].

In the presented work the human glioblastoma cell line U-87 MG is exposed to single nsPEFs with durations of between 2 and 10 ns and electric field intensities of up to of 250 kV/cm. Intracellular calcium concentrations are visualised in real time, during pulse application, using live cell fluorescent imaging. We demonstrate that the level of the increase in calcium concentration can be modulated depending on pulse duration and electric field strength, and that the origin of the calcium (intracellular store vs extracellular media) can also be influenced.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 737164 SUMCASTEC.

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Title

From Eureka to Clinical Trials.

Authors

S. Chaudhry¹.

Affiliations

1. *Afon Technology Ltd, Chepstow, UK.*

Abstract

For diabetics all over the globe and for companies providing blood glucose monitors alike, non-invasive blood glucose monitoring is viewed as the “Holy Grail”. There have been many companies that have attempted to develop such a device and failed! We present here a brief overview of the technologies being developed to crack this golden nut and chart the journey of Afon Technology from the Eureka moment to clinical trials. We will present technical challenges faced by the company and the strategic decisions taken to ensure that we can deliver a product.

Title

The Antimicrobial Efficacy of a Combined RF and Microwave Energy Based Non-Thermal Plasma Generation System; Applications in the Medical Sector.

Authors

R. MS. Thorn¹, G. M. Robinson¹, D. Turner¹, C. Hancock² and D. M. Reynolds¹.

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2. *Creo Medical Limited, Creo House, Unit 2 Beaufort Park, Beaufort Park Way, Chepstow, UK.*

Abstract

A new argon gas based non-thermal plasma system that uses a combination of RF and microwave frequency energy has been developed by Creo Medical Limited with potential applications for sterilisation and disinfection within biological and medical fields. It has multiple advantages for decontamination or sterilisation of hard surfaces as it is non-wetting, does not contain potentially harmful biocides, and it leaves no chemical residue. Within this presentation, the system topology is described and initial results are presented from a microbiological study using the system.

A novel means of striking or igniting the plasma has been developed using a short burst (circa 1 ms) of 100 KHz RF energy. This RF burst is synchronized for a longer duration burst (circa 40 ms) of 2.45 GHz microwave energy to sustain the plasma. The dominant source of energy for the plasma is microwave energy. The energy is delivered as a train of pulses, with a duty cycle of less than 50% and a total treatment time of 200 seconds or less. For antimicrobial studies *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, Methicillin Resistant *S. aureus* and spores of *Bacillus subtilis* were surface associated onto stainless steel coupons. For plasma treatment, the end of the applicator was set to a (vertical) distance of 1 cm from the sample. Argon flow rate was kept constant at 5L min⁻¹ and exposure time was varied at between 10 and 120 seconds (n = 3). In addition, initial 'proof-of-concept' experiments were undertaken to investigate the capability of using non-thermal plasma for decontaminating the operating channel of a medical endoscope device. *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were used to inoculate 10 cm sections of endoscope tubing and subsequently subjected to single static 30 or 60 second non-thermal plasma treatments (n = 4).

The duration of the pulses of 100 KHz and 2.45 GHz energy delivery, treatment time and flow rate of the Ar gas were optimised to ensure the resultant plasma produced the highest possible antimicrobial effect while remaining non-thermal. The results of this study demonstrate that non-thermal plasma system elicited a >3 log reduction against stainless steel surface associated *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and MRSA. However, only a limited antimicrobial effect against spores of *B. subtilis* was observed (<1 log reduction) demonstrating the need for further optimisation of this non-thermal plasma system for sporicidal applications. For the 'proof-of-concept' experiments, it was demonstrated that non-thermal plasma treatment had a significant antimicrobial effect (>5 log reduction) on endoscope tubing loaded with *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa* or *S. aureus*.

This work has demonstrated that a new combined RF and microwave energy based non-thermal plasma generation system has significant antimicrobial efficacy against a range of medically relevant microorganisms. In addition, initial studies have shown that this system

is capable of decontaminating the internal operating lumen of an endoscope device. Future work will focus on development and optimisation of a bespoke non-thermal plasma applicator for effective decontamination of medically relevant microbial biofilms grown within endoscope operating channels.

Title

A Pre-Clinical Assessment of a Medical Microwave Ablation Device in the Treatment of Hepatic Cancer.

Authors

A. Leonard, P. Sibbons¹, A. Southgate and C. Hancock¹ (**Presented by T. Ansari¹**).

Affiliations

1. *Creo Medical, Creo House, Beaufort Park, Beaufort Park Way, Chepstow, UK.*

Abstract

Background: Microwave tissue ablation (MTA) is a treatment by which tumours can be destroyed via coagulation resulting from the passage of microwaves, produced by a medical device, through a tumour mass. The aim of this study was to evaluate the safety and efficacy of such a device, in treating hepatic tumours.

Methods: 20 rats were inoculated with rat hepatoma (HNS) cells via the hepatic portal vein and mesenteric veins. 7 weeks post-inoculation the abdominal cavity was opened, and any tumour within the liver or mesenteric tissue was ablated. Following ablation, animals were terminated and the tissue excised and processed for histological assessment. Two additional animals were recovered, following ablation, for a period of 37 days

Results: The device created discrete areas of ablation, with four specific ablation zones within the ablated tissue being identifiable: A zone of cavitation, a zone of fixation, a zone of vacuolation and a zone of coagulation. The two rats that were recovered appeared to have their tumours completely destroyed with no viable cells present whilst the non-cancerous hepatocytes bordering the area of ablation remained undamaged.

Summary and Conclusions: The device appears to create predictable and successful areas of complete ablation; however, the nature of the cells in the 'fixed zone' requires further investigation.

Title

High Voltage Controllable RF Source and Applicator for Electrosurgical Applications.

Authors

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Abstract

The purpose of this project was to create a High Voltage (circa 400V peak) controllable radio frequency (RF) source for Electrosurgical applications. The source consists of a low voltage (circa 5V peak) oscillator circuit connected to a suitable gate driver circuit that can output enough current to charge up the high input capacitance of a power MOSFET used to drive an output transformer. This is followed by a suitable high frequency toroidal core based output transformer with a shunt connected capacitor across the primary and secondary windings of the transformer to resonate out the inductive reactance of the transformer and also on the secondary side in order to take into account the capacitance of the cable connected to the load. The circuit was tested with the Creo Medical Speedboat™ bipolar electrode and a bespoke bipolar ring electrode for cutting biological tissue. The overall electrosurgical system was designed to cut biological tissue using an electric field created between the two electrodes at an RF frequency of between 20 KHz and 500 KHz (but optimised to operate at a spot frequency of 100 KHz) that is coupled into the biological tissue load. The oscillator was developed utilising an Arduino Uno to allow flexibility with the ability to change both frequency and duty cycle. In this dissertation the use of Arduino Uno based oscillator design is justified and compared to other oscillators. There is a section describing the design process (methodology), including theoretical discussion of the operation of MOSFETs, voltage transformers and resonant filters or methods of reactance cancellation. Sections on the results obtained, discussions, future work and final conclusions are also provided.

Title

Miniature Flexible Microwave Applicator for the Ablation of Pancreatic Tumours at 5.8GHz.

Authors

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Affiliations

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Abstract

A presentation on the initial design for the NP1 or Narrow Probe and how it can be used to treat tumours in the pancreas.

Title

An Advanced System for the Visualisation and Treatment of Cancerous Nodules.

Authors

A. Jones^{1,2}, and S. Preston^{1,2}.

Affiliations

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2. *Creo Medical, Creo House, Beaufort Park, Beaufort Park Way, Chepstow, UK.*

Abstract

Unknown Discussed herein will be the development of both a high resolution, flexible visualisation device and the use of a co-axial transmission line to provide microwave energy and visualisation simultaneously. Use of a CMOS image sensor and LED illumination has provided high resolution images within a 1.6mm inner diameter.

Title

Nano-Imaging of Biological Cells Using High Refractive Index Barium Titanate Glass (BTG) Microspheres on Lab on Chip Platform.

Authors

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Affiliations

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2. *IHP-Leibniz-Institut fuer innovative Mikroelektronik, 15236 Frankfurt (Oder), Germany.*

Abstract

The resolution of classical optical microscope is limited by diffraction limit which is around 200nm in visible range [1]. Several approaches including metal/dielectric based multi-layered super-lens, nanoscale solid immersion lenses and molecular fluorescence microscopy have been proposed to beat the diffraction limit [2]. However, each approaches have their own limitations and drawbacks such as the use of illuminating lasers and metals, which induces the optical losses and affects the performance of metamaterial super-lenses [3]. Moreover, high refractive index dielectric microspheres such as Silica and BTG microspheres have been considered as promising candidates as the replacement of metal based super-lenses due to comparative very low losses and higher transmission in optical range and to image the resolution of plasmonic nanopatterns under white light microscope [4, 5].

However, there are several challenges during the nano-imaging of biological cells flowing through the micro-channel of chip. Working distance between the microspheres and cells

strictly limits the magnification and affects the performance of super-lens in such lab-on-chip platform. Here, we report on significant magnification of *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* (known as *S. Pombe*) yeast cells, flowing through the parallel electrode channel using 80 μm BTG microspheres embedded in thin PDMS film and bonded to the channel of chip.

Figure 1: (a) *S. Pombe* cells (white arrow) flowing through the parallel electrode channel and 80 μm BTG microspheres embedded in thin PDMS film bonded to chip. (b) Magnification of *S. Pombe* cell through BTG microsphere (Blue arrow in figure 1 (a)), while inset reports the movement of cell in the channel.

Figure 1(a) shows the yeast cells flowing along the edge of the channel as indicated by white arrow and the BTG microspheres in PDMS film located on the top of the channel. In this context, magnification of *S. Pombe* through the BTG microspheres located on the edge of channel (indicated by blue arrow in figure 1(a)) has been observed around five times as shown in figure 1(b) and in its inset. We have further exploited dielectrophoresis process to elevate the flowing cells in the channel to further enhance the magnification of cells.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 73Abbe, E. *Archiv Mikroskop. Anat.* 1873, 9, 413.7164 SUMCASTEC.

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Title

UHF-Dielectrophoresis Crossover Frequency Measurements do Allow Discriminating Cancerous Stem Cells from Differentiated Cells.

Authors

R. Manczak¹, S. Saada², M. Tanori³, A. Casciati³, E. Porcù⁶, E. Rampazzo⁶, C. Dalmay¹, B. Bessette², G. Begaud², S. Battu², P. Blondy¹, M. O. Jauberteau², C. B. Kaynak⁴, C. Merla³, B. Tanno³, L. Persano⁶, M. Kaynak⁴, C. Palego⁵, G. Viola⁶, M. Mancuso³, F. Lalloué² and **A. Pothier¹**.

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Abstract

Glioblastoma (GBM) is one of the most frequent and the most aggressive tumor of the central nervous system. About 240,000 brain tumor new cases were diagnosed over the worldwide; the majority are GBMs with an incidence of 3–4 per 100 000 persons per year [1]. Conventional therapeutic strategy is mainly surgery, in combination with chemo- and radiotherapy according to Stupp protocol. Despite recent advances in surgery, imaging, radiation therapies and chemotherapy, the median survival is less than 15 months [2]. This dark prognosis of GBM is primarily due to the recurrence of tumor, which is resistant to precited conventional treatments [1]. Medulloblastoma (MB) is one of the most frequent pediatric malignant brain tumors, commonly found in children between ages of three and ten. Treatments for MB tumors usually include surgery followed by radiation and/or chemotherapy, leading to a 5-year survival rate of 70% to 80% for low-grade tumor that falls down to 60% if tumor has spread to the spinal cord and even decreases down to 30-50% for youngest patients (less than 3 years old) with very aggressive tumor. Especially for most aggressive cases, the tumor presents a stronger resistance to existing treatments that implies a lower therapy efficiency and a tumor relapse.

Limited advances in glioblastoma and medulloblastoma treatment are closely linked to the existence of a restricted cell subpopulation also called cancer stem cells (CSCs), some very immature and undifferentiated cells, responsible for tumor cell heterogeneity [3]. However, even genetically diverse clones express undifferentiated cell markers related to cancer stem cells such as CD133 and CD44. The higher expression levels of CD133 have been correlated to poorer prognosis suggesting that this marker might play a significant role in the resistance of this type of cancer to chemotherapy and radiotherapy [4]. Other markers such as the transcription factors OCT-4, SOX2, pSTAT3 and NANOG are considered as key players in regulating transcription of glioblastoma CSCs [3]. These CSCs are a subpopulation of undifferentiated cells, which have specific biological properties similar to normal stem cells. Currently, biologists used some immunostaining approaches to characterize CSC populations, as flow cytometry, optical microscopy or protein array analysis, based on targeting a set of undifferentiated markers previously described. These markers are required to validate the stemness lineage of CSCs from the huge heterogeneous cell population. Nevertheless, CSCs subpopulation are very rare in

tumors and their isolation often requires enriching them in specific culture medium. This strategy is time consuming and makes the results longer. Currently, the key objective is to try to get around this problem by establishing a new way to discriminate and sort undifferentiated cell populations independently of their biological and physical characteristics.

To help medical researchers and scientists to improve cancer diagnosis, prognosis and patient medical conditions, many different techniques have been implemented. Bioelectric signals from cells have been proved to carry various useful information about the cell status [5]. Many sources of cell bioelectric signals like sodium potassium channels and pumps in the plasma membrane, effect of chemical analytes, cell patterning and cell-to-cell interactions with the extracellular matrix can be determined by exploiting the dielectric properties. Among these techniques, Dielectrophoresis (DEP) is a label-free, accurate, fast, and low-cost analysis method that uses the principles of polarization and the motion of bio-particles in applied electric fields [6]. The efficiency of this technique has been proved in various fields, including polymer research, environmental and medical research, biosensors, microfluidics and diagnosis based on microfluidic biosensors [7]. Actually, this technique can also help to sort lowly represented cell subpopulations, such as cancer stem cells, hidden within other heterogeneous differentiated cells.

In the presented work, we show a new approach for undifferentiated cells detection and characterization based on microwave dielectric spectroscopy in the Ultra High Frequency range (UHF), using DEP cell electromanipulation [8] based on microfluidic Lab-on-Chip methodology. This approach offers unique capabilities to investigate the intracellular dielectric properties and allows screening of the intracellular biological properties and differences within the heterogeneity of a tumor.

Microscope imaging sequence of GBM cell crossover frequency measurement using Lab-on-Chip microsystem and difference of UHF DEP signature between differentiated (NN) vs undifferentiated (DN) GBM cell line subpopulations

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 737164 SUMCASTEC.

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Title

Creating Biological Scaffolds and Matrices for Clinical Application.

Authors

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Abstract

As the world's population ages and the incidence of certain diseases increases, there is a growing demand for functional tissues and organs. This demand may be for organ transplantation (e.g. liver) or to replace or repair damaged tissue e.g. sport injury (e.g. cruciate ligament) or trauma (skin wounds or burns). This requirement for additional tissue cannot currently be met through routine organ donation and it is obvious that an alternative solution is needed. One potential solution is to use a tissue engineering or regenerative medicine approach, whereby scaffolds and cells are combined in the laboratory with the attempt to create functional tissue.

This presentation sets out to illustrate how functional organs and tissue might be created in the laboratory. It covers the basic requirements of the different scaffolds (both synthetic and biologics) and cell types and the assessment processes used to analyse the product. Finally, examples from different biological systems are used to illustrate what has been currently achieved.

Title

Potential Use of Porcine Gastro-Intestinal Organoids for Pharmacological Applications.

Authors

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Abstract

Recently, there has been a rise in the use of organoids for several molecular and biological applications ranging from developmental biology to pharmacological applications [1, 2]. Organoids are three-dimensional (3D) in vitro self-replicating and self-organizing structures that resemble their in vivo counterpart [1]. Because they retain the in vivo tissue physiological phenotypes, they have great potentials as a platform for several biological applications. The gastro-intestinal tract (GI) is crucial for the normal body's growth and development. However, its dysregulation can lead to a number of diseases. Hence, one of the major limitations of finding effective treatment for such diseases is the lack of appropriate models that fully recapitulate the in vivo pathology. A major contributing factor is also the inappropriate choice of species with implications for translational relevance during the preclinical screening of new therapies for efficacy and safety.

Here, we present the culture and establishment of porcine GI organoids and their potential use as a tool in safety assessment of small molecules (Fig. 1). In addition, knowing the diverse complexity of the emerging 3D organoids, they offer a good near in vivo physiological micro-environment for cell spectral signature analysis. Building upon the foundational work of cell spectral signature analysis in 2D cancer cell platforms (undifferentiated and differentiated), it is highly likely that the use of 3D organoids will be a suitable replacement. If the proof of concept is established in 3D organoids, the findings here will provide an invaluable information to the field of micro-optofluidic lab-on-chip technology. Additionally, where devices have a potential cellular impact, initial in vitro assessment may help streamline device development more efficiently.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram illustrating the potential use of porcine organoids in safety assessment of compounds

In conclusion, given the close genetic homology between pigs and humans and their similar organ size, they offer an alternative source of organoids to those generated from small rodents; offering an improved cost-benefit outcome of large animal use and translational relevance.

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Interactive Poster Presentations

Poster #1:

The Biological Effects of Microwave Electric Fields on Bacterial and Yeast Cells and Applications in Pathogen Detection.

Authors

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Abstract

Mycobacterium abscessus (*M. abscessus*), is a pathogen commonly isolated from patients with cystic fibrosis¹. Antibiotic treatment is no longer reliable due to multiple drug resistance². Currently, there is no rapid diagnostic tool to detect the presence of *M. abscessus*³. Rapid diagnosis followed by appropriate, prompt treatment remains the best curative approach to mitigate disease burden and halt transmission. A major bottle neck in developing a rapid diagnostic assay is DNA extraction. Mycobacterial cells are very difficult to lyse, the existing methods are time consuming resulting in long turnaround time to detect the pathogen. The ability of microwaves to release DNA from bacterial cells has been reported by mechanisms which have yet to be determined. The disruptive effects of microwaves on biological structures has been attributed to the local generation of heat while the contribution, if any, of non-thermal factors has yet to be determined.

The aims of this study are to develop a microwave-based DNA assay capable of detecting *M. abscessus* within a short time frame and to investigate the type of interaction of microwaves E, H or E+H fields with cell membranes of a range of structurally diverse microorganisms (Gram-negative, Gram-positive, mycobacteria and yeast). Based on published genome sequences, DNA probes which targeted the *rpoB* and *erm-41* genes of *M. abscessus* were designed. Using previously isolated DNA and a magnetic-bead-based sandwich hybridisation assay, isolates of *M. abscessus* were distinguished from non-*M. abscessus* isolates within 70 mins with a lower detection limit of 10 fg/uL. To study the interaction of microwaves with cell membranes, the structure which represents the major barrier to DNA release, a confocal microscopy was employed to examine the passage of different sized fluorescent dextran particles (3, 10 and 70 kDa) into bacterial cells following microwave exposure. The results show a transient disruption of cells membrane, leading to the influx of dextran particles in a size dependent manner and the efflux of intracellular DNA. Understanding how non-thermal MW mediates biological effects will help in the development and maximisation of the potential of microwaves in various aspects of application.

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Poster #2:

A Novel Miniature Tissue Resection Device with Moveable Jaws that Combines 400 KHz and 5.8G Hz Energy for Cutting and Coagulation.

Authors

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Abstract

A new electrosurgical device with articulating jaws that is capable of delivering 400KHz and 5.8GHz energy for cutting and coagulation of biological tissue respectively. The device has two miniature (4mm length) articulating jaws that form a microwave antenna to deliver energy at 5.8GHz and two opposing poles that form a bipolar structure to deliver energy at 400KHz. The device overcomes challenges associated with voltage breakdown when delivering 400KHz energy with a peak voltage of up to 350V for cutting and antenna to tissue impedance match when delivering 5.8GHz energy to produce dielectric heating.

Poster #3:

An example of a Medical Microwave System Developed by Members of the Group for the Treatment and Measurement of Breast Tumours.

Authors

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Abstract

The MicroBlate System is a cancer detection and treatment system for open or percutaneous tumour ablation that uses microwave energy in the Super High Frequency (SHF) band to identify and controllably ablate cancerous tissue and a well defined safe margin. The system uses a sensitive (<-70 dB) low power millimetre wave measurement system or transceiver to measure the complex impedance of tissue as the 2mm diameter 120mm long rigid antenna is pushed into the tissue. The transceiver enables the boundary between healthy and cancerous tissue to be detected to determine the edge of the tumour. Once a first boundary is recognised, the antenna is moved through the tumour until a second boundary is identified, then the tip of the antenna is pulled back halfway to mark the centre of the lesion. The high power millimetre wave source is then switch on to ablate the tumour, where the tissue is controllable 'cooked' from the inside out. A proprietary means of dynamically impedance matching the antenna to the changing impedance of the tissue is also activated to ensure that the demanded dose of energy is delivered into the tumour with a predetermined safe margin.

Poster #4:

Electrosurgical Applicator Radio Frequency; 100kHz 400V pk– pk Generator.

Authors

E. Waller.

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Abstract

The following project is a useful explanation in the generation a simple RF Source which has practical applications in Electrosurgery. This Project has led to the creation of a few conceptual ideas including a wireless transmission system for Electro-surgical applications and various applicator designs aimed at improving efficiency and effectiveness of RF cutting.

Poster #5:

Ultrashort Electric Field Pulse Generator using Avalanche Breakdown Transistors and the Open Circuit Transmission Line Technique.

Authors

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Creo Medical, Creo House, Beaufort Park, Beaufort Park Way, Chepstow, UK.*

Abstract

An ultrashort electric field pulse generator based on relatively slow charging and ultrafast discharging of a co-axial transmission line in conjunction with a stack of low-cost avalanche breakdown transistors which operate as a fast switching element has been designed and built. This low-cost circuit design produces well defined ultrashort electric field pulses with symmetrical rise and fall times of less than 2 ns. The pulse duration is determined by the length of the open-circuit transmission line. Initial results indicate that the circuit is capable of generating well defined nanosecond electroporation pulses to support nanosecond-pulse based applications in biology, medicine and/or in a cost-effective manner

Poster #6:

Push-Pull Configuration of High Power MOSFETs for Generation of Nanosecond Pulses for Electroporation of Medulloblastoma Cells.

Authors

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Creo Medical, Creo House, Beaufort Park, Beaufort Park Way, Chepstow, UK.*

Abstract

A power MOSFET-based push-pull configuration nanosecond-pulse generator has been designed, constructed, and characterized to permeabilize cells for biological and medical applications. The generator can deliver pulses with durations ranging from 80ns up to 1 μ s and pulse amplitudes up to 1.4kV. The unit has been tested for in-vitro experiments on a medulloblastoma cell line.

Following the exposure of cells to 100ns, 200ns and 300ns electric field pulses, permeabilization tests were carried out, and viability tests were conducted to verify the performance of the generator. The maximum temperature rise of the biological load was also calculated based on Joule heating energy conservation and experimental validation.

Our results indicate that the developed device has good capabilities to achieve well controlled electro-manipulation invitro.

Poster #7:

μ Pulse Electric Fields Exposure Targeting Medulloblastoma Cancer Stem Cells.

Authors

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Abstract

Medulloblastoma (MB) is the most common pediatric malignant brain tumor in which cancer stem cells (CSCs) seem to be candidates in the onset of the disease, constitute an endless reserve for the maintenance and progression of the tumor and, furthermore, they could be the reason of conventional therapy failure. Therefore, new therapeutic strategies are necessary to targeting specifically CSCs. The goal of this study is to selectively target quiescent malignant CSCs and subsequently induce a differentiation process to sensitize them to radiotherapy treatment using appropriately modulated pulse electric fields (PEFs).

To this aim, different μ PEFs are been selected to exposure D283Med cells, resulted to be a perfect model of MB CSCs, and normal human astrocytes. In particular, the μ PEF-3 (40 μ s 0.35 MV/m 5pulses) exposure induced a different response in term of cell death and cell cycle perturbation. To provide deep insight into the mechanism that differentiate the response, we focus our attention on the cell cycle network, using the RT2 Profiler PCR Arrays. Results showed that μ PEF-3 induced the G2/M arrest via the up-regulation of GADD45a that could be crucial for the choice of the cell fate activating apoptosis, senescence or differentiation mediated by stress-activated p38 MAPK process.

Our results suggest that this new therapeutic approach could be used to neutralize CSCs or as pretreatment to promote radiosensitization.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 737164 SUMCASTEC

Poster #8:

Human Medulloblastoma Cell Lines: Investigating on Cancer Stem Cell-Like Phenotype.

Authors

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6. *University of Limoges, Captur, EA3842, F-87000 Limoges, France.*
- 7.

Abstract

Medulloblastoma (MB) is the most common malignant pediatric brain tumor; despite the progress of new treatments including surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy, the risk of recurrence, morbidity and death remains important and the long-term adverse effects in survivors are substantial. The fraction of cancer stem cell-like (CSCs) within a brain tumor, with their self-renewal ability and multi-lineage differentiation potential, is critical of tumor initiation, growth and resistance to therapies, impacting on the survival of patients with "poor-prognosis". For new CSC-targeting therapies, further in depth studies are needed using enriched and stable MB-CSCs populations. This work, aimed at identifying the amount of CSCs in three available human cell lines (DAOY, D341 and D283), describing different approaches based on the expression of stemness markers evaluated by in vitro and in vivo assays. First, we explored potential differences in gene and protein expression patterns of specific stem cell markers. Then, in order to identify and discriminate undifferentiated from differentiated cells, MB cells were also characterized using a physical characterization method based on a high frequency dielectrophoresis approach, complementary to cell biological features. Finally, we compared their tumorigenic potential in vivo, through engrafting in nude mice. Concordantly, our findings identify the D283 human cell line as an ideal model of CSCs, providing important evidence on the use of a commercial human MB cell line for the development of new strategic CSC-targeting therapies.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 737164 SUMCASTEC

Poster #9:

Microsystem and Lab-On-Chip Technologies Might Promote Future Generation of New Tools for Biological Analysis: Example of New Type of Cell Sorting Microsystem Taking Advantage of High Frequency Dielectrophoresis Specificities of Cancerous Cells.

Authors

T. Provent¹, R. Manczak¹, S. Saada², C. Dalmay¹, B. Bessette², G. Begaud², S. Battu², P. Blondy¹, M. O. Jauberteau², F. Lalloué² and A. Pothier¹.

Affiliations

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2. Univ. Limoges, CAPTuR EA3842, F-87000 Limoges, France.

Abstract

In the biomedical field, the sorting of cells is prime of importance in a large range of applications including the development of diagnostic and therapeutic tools but also in cellular biology. In recent years, with the progress of microfluidics and lab-on-chip technologies, researchers have focused their attention on the development of novel label free cell sorting technics. The main motivation is to avoid any type of labels, like biochemical molecules, metallic or magnetic beads that can modify the biological cell to analyze but also to make experimentations less expensive, complex and time consuming.

Label free cell sorting technics are non-invasive methods based on cells physical characteristics, like their size, density, optical or dielectric properties. In this context, dielectrophoresis (DEP) technics appears very attractive.

Indeed, the DEP principle is based on the interaction between a dielectric particle, here a biological cell, and a non-uniform electric field, which generate displacement forces on cells.

This paper is focused on Ultra-high Frequencies dielectrophoresis (UHF-DEP) working in the hundreds of MHz frequency range. Recently, some research works using UHF-DEP have been led especially due to the fact that high frequencies allows bypassing the cell membrane. Consequently, generated DEP forces are strongly linked to the intracellular properties. It may allow to probe and characterize the dielectric specificities in a non-destructive way (no cell lysis required) of the intracellular content of individual cells.

Photograph of prototyped microfluidic based cell lab-on-chip cell sorter and example of on chip cell sorting

The objective of this current research work is to develop a new generation of UHF-DEP cell cytometer to illustrate how powerful might be such technologies, especially in the frame of Cancer Stem Cell studies, where conventional cell sorting approaches lack from efficiency due to current lack of reliable and specific immunostaining markers.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 737164 SUMCASTEC.

Poster #10:

Glioblastoma Cancer Stem-like Cells Discrimination by UHF-Dielectrophoresis Crossover Frequency.

Authors

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Abstract

SUMCASTEC* explores new approach for cancer stem cells (CSCs) real time and neutralization, by developing a micro- optofluidic lab-on-chip (LOC) platform.

Cancer Stem Cells or CSCs appear as major biological and therapeutic targets, in particular for Glioblastoma (GBM). Heterogeneity of tumor cell populations, leads to optimize characterization and sorting methods. Actually, analysis are based on efficiently targeting of a set of biological markers, which are used to validate the cell stemness properties.

Besides the biological properties, biophysical properties of CSCs are expected to be a potential way to discriminate, sort and finally neutralize CSC populations. Our data summarize first's results glioblastoma cell lines' and GBM primary cultures characterization; measuring their crossover frequencies by di-electrophoresis (DEP) technics using Ultra High frequency (UHF) range (above 50 MHz).

In order to establish the proof of concept, GBM cell lines are cultured following different conditions, in order to achieve an enrichment of CSCs. In other hand, CD133 marker-based sorting is assessed to discriminate CSC of GBM primary cultures subpopulations and characterize their crossover frequencies.

Using microfluidic lab-on-chip systems implemented on Bipolar-Complementary Oxide Semiconductor (BiCMOS) technology (allowing single cell handling and analysis), and following DEP electrokinetic method, these CSCs were discriminated from the differentiated cells. Based on measurements of their own intracellular specificities, the enriched CSCs subpopulations have shown clear differences of DEP crossover frequency signatures of CSC enriched populations compared to differentiated cells.

That demonstrates the concept and validates the technique efficiency for CSCs discrimination. Confirming a high potential of the LOC platform in the diagnosis and development of new glioblastoma therapeutics.

*SUMCASTEC (Semiconductor-based Ultrawideband Micromanipulation of Cancer STEM Cells)

Poster #11:

Potential use of Porcine Gastro-Intestinal Organoids for Safety Assessment of Current and Novel Chemical Entities.

Authors

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3. *Creo Medical, Creo House, Beaufort Park, Beaufort Park Way, Chepstow, UK.*

Abstract

Recently, there has been a rise in the use of organoids for several molecular and biological applications ranging from developmental biology to pharmacological applications [1, 2]. Organoids are three-dimensional (3D) in vitro self-replicating and self-organizing structures that resemble their in vivo counterpart [1]. Because they retain the in vivo tissue physiological phenotypes, they have great potentials as a platform for several biological applications. The gastro-intestinal tract (GI) is crucial for the normal body's growth and development. However, its dysregulation can lead to a number of diseases. Hence, one of the major limitations of finding effective treatment for such diseases is the lack of appropriate models that fully recapitulate the in vivo pathology. A major contributing factor is also the inappropriate choice of species with implications for translational relevance during the preclinical screening of new therapies for efficacy and safety.

Here, we present the culture and establishment of porcine GI organoids and their potential use as a tool in safety assessment of small molecules (Fig. 1). In addition, knowing the diverse complexity of the emerging 3D organoids, they offer a good near in vivo physiological micro-environment for cell spectral signature analysis. Building upon the foundational work of cell spectral signature analysis in 2D cancer cell platforms (undifferentiated and differentiated), it is highly likely that the use of 3D organoids will be a suitable replacement. If the proof of concept is established in 3D organoids, the findings here will provide an invaluable information to the field of micro-optofluidic lab-on-chip technology. Additionally, where devices have a potential cellular impact, initial in vitro assessment may help streamline device development more efficiently.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram illustrating the potential use of porcine organoids in safety assessment of compounds

In conclusion, given the close genetic homology between pigs and humans and their similar organ size, they offer an alternative source of organoids to those generated from small rodents; offering an improved cost-benefit outcome of large animal use and translational relevance.

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Poster #12:

A Prototype System for Visualising and Treating Early Stage Cancerous Nodules within the Lungs.

Authors

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Abstract

The poster shows the development of a flexible 1.6mm outer diameter visualisation device. With the use of a catheter it can be navigated deep into the bronchial tree and retracted/inserted as needed to allow for the use of other endoscopic tools such as a microwave ablation probe. The design and manufacturing of a laser cut part has allowed for a consistent placement of the image sensor and LEDs which in turn have helped improve the images and durability of the device.